

Enhanced Safe and Sustainable
coatings for supporting the Planet

NEWSLETTER

Issue 1, JULY 2023

IN THIS ISSUE:

1. PROPLANET concept
2. Interview with our coordinator
3. PROPLANET website and Social media
4. PROPLANET Dissemination material
5. Attendance to events
6. Upcoming events
7. Press releases
8. PROPLANET joined the ECOSYSTEX network
9. Our cluster starts taking a form
10. Meet the PROPLANET consortium

www.proplanet-project.eu | info@proplanet-project.eu

Funded by the European Union under the GA no **101091842**.
Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s)
only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or
HADEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can
be held responsible for them.

PROPLANET CONCEPT

The primary objective of PROPLANET is to develop and optimize three cutting-edge coatings finding several applications among which in textile, food packaging machines, and glass industries. These coatings are intended to be a cost-effective, highly functional, safe, and sustainable alternative to existing coatings containing per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS).

In the textile sector, PROPLANET aims to create an innovative coating solution that provides enhanced functionality, durability, and sustainability. This coating will offer improved properties such as water and oil repellency, stain resistance, and easy-to-clean characteristics, ensuring the longevity and performance of textile products while minimizing the environmental impact.

For the food packaging industry, PROPLANET focuses on developing a coating that meets the stringent requirements of food safety and regulatory standards. The coating will exhibit properties such as barrier protection, anti-corrosion, and resistance to high temperatures, ensuring the preservation and integrity of food products while eliminating the use of PFAS-based coatings.

In the glass sector, PROPLANET aims to design a novel coating that provides anti-soiling, self-cleaning, and anti-reflective properties. This coating will minimize the accumulation of dirt, reduce the need for frequent cleaning, and enhance the transparency and clarity of glass surfaces, offering improved functionality and aesthetic appeal.

Moreover, computational tools will be developed within the project that aim to support the characterisation activities to optimise the design. PROPLANET will therefore develop a fully detailed roadmap to ensure all the results meet the criteria of the latest standards and regulations, aiming for product development and upscaling from TRL3 to TRL5. Furthermore, the project will screen and list a set of environmental certifications, in order to establish a framework to enable a self-declaration that ensures that high sustainability criteria are followed.

By creating advanced coatings, PROPLANET strives to offer viable alternatives to PFAS-based coatings in the targeted industries. The project's goal is to provide cost-effective, high-performing, safe, and sustainable solutions that align with the principles of circular economy and contribute to a healthier and more environmentally friendly future.

Overall, the safe and sustainable by design approaches employed in PROPLANET ensure that the developed coatings not only offer enhanced functionality and performance but also contribute to a more sustainable and responsible future for the targeted industries.

INTERVIEW WITH OUR COORDINATOR

In this issue, we have the privilege of sharing the interview of the PROPLANET coordinator. The project aims to revolutionize the coatings industry with safe and sustainable alternatives. We will delve into the objectives, approaches, and achievements of the project, shedding light on its innovative contributions to the textile, food packaging and glass sectors. Let's hear from our coordinator, **Dr. Johannes Seif**, about the exciting goals and developments of PROPLANET.

Dr Johannes Seif holds a Master degree in Physics and a Ph.D. in Science. Throughout his career he worked both in research (EPFL, UNSW, Fraunhofer ISE) and in industry (Meyer Burger Research, INDEOtec). At all these institutions he focused on the development of crystalline silicon heterojunction solar cells and of plasma enhanced chemical vapor deposition processes for the deposition of thin films. Currently he is working at IDENER as a project manager and engineer and is leading the HORIZON EUROPE project PROPLANET.

1. What are the main objectives and expected outcomes of the PROPLANET project?

Due to their unique chemical properties PFAS (per- and poly-fluoroalkyl substances) were widely used in various industrial sectors. They are e.g. well-known for their anti-stick properties, useful for pans and pots, but are also used in many other products, ranging from firefighting foams to glass coatings. Since they do not break down in the environment they represent a serious health threat as they accumulate there. In PROPLANET we are striving to replace PFAS by more sustainable alternatives. To achieve this we will develop SSbD coatings based on crosslinked biopolymers or siloxane that will be validated in the textile, the glass and the food packaging machines industry. Also this development will be backed by mathematical tools such as first-principle, in silico and environmental fate models to assess the new coatings sustainability and replicate their behavior in different settings. PROPLANET will have an impact on different levels. The outcomes will help to reduce human exposure to harmful substances, increase social acceptance and push for new regulations for

manufacturing processes. Furthermore, the new coatings will increase the recoverability and recyclability of the products, promote a circular value chain and reduce the overall environmental impact. Finally, a set of multi-scale computational tools will be developed along with SSbD criteria and principles and knowledge in circular manufacture.

2. What are the specific technologies or innovations being developed within the PROPLANET project and how do they contribute to the development of environmentally friendly coating materials?

In PROPLANET we are developing three different types of PFAS alternatives, (i) crosslinked biopolymers oil/wax microcapsules based on a polysaccharide matrix, (ii) bio-based hybrid siloxane coatings and (iii) hybrid siloxane coatings. All three have one thing in common, they are all fluorine-free and adhere therefore to the SSbD principles. Ideally they will perform as well or better than the currently used PFAS coatings. The PROPLANET replication tool on the other hand, will help to pave the way for future developments of such

INTERVIEW WITH OUR COORDINATOR

PFAS-free SSbD coatings and give the user further insights how a specific material will perform in different situations.

3. Which are the PROPLANET targeted sectors and how does the project contribute to addressing their environmental and sustainability challenges?

The three coating materials mentioned before, will be applied in the textile, the food packaging machines

and the glass coating industry. Across these three, but also across many other sectors, PFAS are currently widely used. The goal of PROPLANET is to provide solutions that completely avoid PFAS and adhere to the SSbD guidelines. This will contribute to a reduction of emissions of harmful substances, but also enable the sectors to enter in a truly circular economy which will help the companies to achieve their environmental and sustainability goals.

PROPLANET WEBSITE AND SOCIAL MEDIA

Our PROPLANET project was developed since month 2 of the project and sheds some light on various aspects, including the project's concept and methodology, the consortium involved, the Dissemination and communications) Toolkit, and the latest news and announcements. Through these components, we aim to provide a comprehensive understanding of the project's objectives, approach, and progress.

Visit our proplanet website:

www.proplanet-project.eu

PROPLANET utilizes various social media platforms, including LinkedIn, Facebook, and Twitter, as channels to disseminate news, updates and accomplishments to stakeholders, academia, and the wider public. These platforms serve as valuable tools for increasing visibility and engagement, ensuring that the project's progress reaches a broader audience. Moreover, social media enables active stakeholder participation, providing a platform for project consortium to receive feedback and stimulate meaningful discussions.

PROPLANET Twitter:

PROPLANET LinkedIn:

PROPLANET Facebook:

PROPLANET DISSEMINATION MATERIAL

We are happy to present our official project identity and our communication material available in our website:

www.proplanet-project.eu/dc-printed-materials

Official Logo

LOGO COLOURS

LOGO FONT: ARIAL

PROPLANET Leaflet

PROPLANET Poster

PROPLANET Rollup

PROPLANET Folder

PROPLANET Badge

ATTENDANCE TO EVENTS

NovaMechanics attended the NanoSAFE Conference that took place on June 5th - 9th, 2023 in Grenoble (France). The conference is organized every two years in Grenoble since 2008, and aims to share the latest research results on health and safety issues related to nanomaterials and beyond.

IDENER, NILU and NovaMechanics participated in the RiskGONE final workshop that took place on the 16th of June 2023. The event as organised by NILU in Madrid.

UPCOMING EVENTS

The PROPLANET consortium has identified additional forthcoming dissemination initiatives with the objective of maximizing the project's visibility and influence. Consortium partners will take an active role in conferences and exhibitions dedicated to the bio-based coatings domain. These events provide an ideal platform to showcase research findings, innovations, and project achievements to a wider audience. By participating in these gatherings, partners will engage in discussions, establish connections with industry experts, and contribute to the widespread dissemination of knowledge within the field.

PARTNER	EVENT	DATE: DD/MM	LOCATION	WEBSITE
TECNALIA	European Silicon Days	10 - 12 July 2023	Montpellier (France)	LINK
TECNALIA	SMT 35 - 35 th International Conference on Surface Modification Technologies	18-22 September 2023	Hamburg, Germany	LINK
AITEX	X Congreso I+D+i "Creando Sinergias" (Polytechnic University of Valencia)	05-06 July 2023	Alcoi, Spain	LINK
AITEX	ECOFIRA 2023	14-16 November 2023	Valencia, Spain	LINK
AITEX	Aachen-Dresden-Denkendorf International Textile Conference 2023	30 November - 01 December 2023	Aachen-Dresden (Germany)	LINK
AITEX	AUTEX 2024 Conference	TBC	Liberec, Czech Republic	LINK
NILU	Eurotox	September 10-13, 2023, 2024 and 2025 (TBD)	2023 in Ljubljana, 2024 and 2025 TBD	LINK
NILU	Joint 3R symposium	19-21 September 2023	Brussels, Belgium	LINK
RINA	SUSGEM2023	23 Oct 2023	Castelló de la Plana, Spain	LINK
RINA & TECNALIA	International Sol-Gel Conference, 2024	2024 (TBD)	TBD	TBD

PRESS RELEASES

PROPLANET has taken advantage of various communication channels to increase its visibility and impact. In addition to being featured in a newsletter and bulletin, the project has released its first press release in both English and Spanish.

PROPLANET JOINED THE ECOSYSTEX NETWORK

In early 2023, ECOSYSTEX, the European Community of Practice for a Sustainable Textile Ecosystem, was officially launched with the objective of fostering collaboration in the field of textile sustainability and circularity. This initiative, facilitated by the Textile ETP and supported by the European Commission's Research Executive Agency (REA), the European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HaDEA), and the Circular-Biobased Europe Joint Undertaking, aims to establish a cohesive and enduring community of practice that promotes cooperation among textile circularity projects.

PROPLANET recently joined the ECOSYSTEX network and participates in several working groups meetings periodically. By bringing together various project consortia, ECOSYSTEX seeks to create a platform for long-term

collaboration, ensuring that knowledge exchange and joint efforts continue beyond the individual durations of each project. The network will enable participants to share best practices, innovative ideas, and research outcomes in the textile sustainability and circularity domain. Through the collaborative efforts facilitated by ECOSYSTEX, the textile industry can make significant strides towards achieving a more sustainable and circular ecosystem.

You may find out more here:

www.linkedin.com/showcase/ecosystex/

OUR CLUSTER STARTS TAKING A FORM

Our cluster is beginning to take shape as we initiate communication with the project coordinator and dissemination manager of IRISS project, which stands for "The International ecosystem for accelerating the transition to Safe-and-Sustainable-by design materials, products, and processes." This collaboration marks an important step forward in our collective efforts towards promoting safe and sustainable practices in material development and manufacturing.

By engaging with IRISS, we aim to foster knowledge exchange, collaboration, and synergy among our respective projects. The focus on safe and sustainable design aligns with our cluster's shared vision of creating a more environmentally friendly and socially responsible ecosystem. Through this partnership, we can leverage each other's expertise and resources to accelerate the transition towards safer and more sustainable materials, products, and processes.

You may find out more about the project by following this link :

www.ivl.se/english/ivl/project/iriss.html

MEET OUR FIRST 4 MEMBERS OF OUR CONSORTIUM

* Find more of our consortium members in the next PROPLANET newsletter...

IDENER is the project coordinator and is a Spanish private research organisation with expertise in the multidisciplinary field of Computational Science that will ensure proper inputs to the models and accurate data gathering of results.

idener
SCIENTIFIC COMPUTING

TECNALIA is the largest center of applied research and technological development in Spain. Their surface engineering department is developing coating and surface modification processes, specifically for each industrial need, as well as providing characterisation facilities.

tecnalia
MEMBER OF BASQUE RESEARCH
& TECHNOLOGY ALLIANCE

exelisis

EXELISIS is an SME located in Greece, with a large experience in providing solutions for exploitation and marketing activities concerning innovative products and research-based results, in the field of engineering, energy, waste & recycling management, business, and sustainable agriculture, among others.

PROPLANET

Enhanced Safe and
Sustainable coatings for
supporting the Planet

aitex[®]
research & innovation center

AITEX is Spain's leading centre for research, innovation and advanced technical services for the textile, garment and technical textile industries. AITEX is one of the project's end users validating the developed coatings on technical textiles.

PROPLANET

Enhanced Safe and Sustainable coatings for supporting the Planet

www.proplanet-project.eu
info@proplanet-project.eu

#PROPLANET

PROPLANET PARTNERS

Funded by
the European Union

Funded by the European Union under the GA no 101091842. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or HADEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.